

Concept of Netra *Patalas* in Ayurveda

Dr. Supriya Prasanna Doke¹.

Prof. Dr. Mrs. Nilakshi. S. Pradhan.²

1. M.S. Shalakyatantra P.G. Scholar. 2. Principal, H.O.D. , Guide
(Shalakyatantra) SSAM Hadapsar, Pune.

Abstracts

Ayurveda the ancient science of India has described the eye in detail with respect to its anatomy, physiology and diseases along with their treatment. Most detailed description of *Netra* is found in the *Uttartantra* of *Sushrut samhita*. *Sushruta* has described *Netra Sharira*, *Nidana*, and *Chikitsa* under three distinct parts called *Mandala*, *Patalas* and *Sandhi*. For better interpretation of a disease a clear anatomical knowledge is important. The objective of this research paper is detail study of *Patalas* and their nearest correlation with eye anatomy.

Key word: *Patala*, *Netra*, Eye, Layer.

Introduction

Shalakyatantra is a specialized branch of *Ayurveda*. *Sushruta* has described *Netra Sharira* in detail under three parts *mandala*, *Patalas* and *Sandhi*. *Mandala* are five in number, *Patalas* and *sandhi* are six¹ in number.

The word *Patala* is used to denote different parts of the eye in different context. The fact regarding the *Netra Patalas* adopted by ancient surgeons is still a matter of debate.

Anatomy explained in *Ayurveda* is parallel to modern anatomy which is now very well developed and with its acquired knowledge an appropriate modern resemblance is figured out for all anatomy described in *Ayurveda*.

Patala is one of the anatomical structures in eyeball described in *Ayurveda* which invites different opinions by various scholars. But a clinic-anatomical approach to the problem by considering different eye diseases and their signs and symptoms pertaining to a particular anatomical structure can solve this issue. With the help of this study the *Patalas* are closely correlated with eye anatomy and it helps with diagnosis of disease with this correlation of *Ayurvedic* diseases with Modern diseases which are described in ophthalmology and concisely treat them with *Ayurvedic* basis of treatment.

Aim and Objective:

- 1) To study the detailed knowledge of *Patalas* according to *Ayurveda*.
- 2) The objective of this research paper is study the detailed knowledge of *Patalas* and their nearest correlation with eye anatomy.

Concept of *Patala*

Patalas are six in number -Two *Bahya patala* and four *Abhyantar patala*.

A. *Bahya Patala*

Two *Bahya Patalas* are *Vartmagat patalas*² (eyelids).

B. *Abhyantara Patala*

1. *Tejojalaashrita patala*³

- 1) It is the outermost among the four *Patalas* and also covers the *Drishti*⁴ *mandala*.
- 2) According to *Sushruta* first or *Bahya patala* is constituted by or lying in *Teja* and *Jala mahabhutas*.
- 3) Whereas *Dalhana* is of the opinion that this *Patala* is constituted by *Rakta*.
- 4) *Vagbhata*, while describing the *Srotas* or *Doshic* constitution of *Netra*, states that *Raktavaha strotasa* forms the black part of *Netra* i.e., *Krushna mandala* (corneal part) and *Kaphavaha strotas* constitutes the *Shweta mandala* (scleral part). It is known fact that *Rakta* represents *Teja* while *Kapha* represents the *Jala mahabhuta* in the human body.
- 5) The only clinical feature of first *Patala* pathology is blurred vision which sometimes become clear without any symptom i.e., refractive error which could be corrected by accommodation.
- 6) In the chapter of *Dristigataroga*, blurring of vision or *Avyakta roopa darshana*⁵ has been mentioned as important symptom of *Timira*⁶ when it involves the first *Patala*.
- 7) Corneal involvement occurs in refractive error like Myopia, Hypermetropia⁷ etc, where blurring of vision found a key feature.
- 8) According to clinical features of first *Patala* it can be nearly correlated with Refractive errors in modern science.

2 *Mansaashrita Patala*⁸

- 1) First *Patala* being outer second lies inner to the former.
- 2) It is constituted by *Mansa* (muscular structure) having *Kandara* (tendon) like properties of giving attachment. It should have nutritive as well as contraction and relaxation properties.
- 3) Structures inner to first *Patala* (cornea and sclera) having such properties is uveal tract i.e, Iris, Ciliary body and Choroid.
- 4) Clinical features of second *Patala* according to *Sushruta* and *Vagbhata*⁹.
 - a) More dimness of vision(*Drushtimandya*).
 - b) Floaters in the visual field.
 - c) He visualizes distant object as if nearer and near object far away due to faulty perception.

- d) Cannot pass thread through needle.
- e) Diplopia.
- 5) Accommodation¹⁰ means the capacity to focus object at different distance in quick succession.
- 6) This phenomenon in human being is brought about by two distinct components of ciliary body and physical component of the lens.
- 7) Thus it is concluded that the morphological, physiological and pathological characters of second *Patala* are alike uveal tract (ciliary body, iris, choroid)¹¹.

3 *Medoashrita Patala*.¹²

- 1) Third *Patala* lies inner to the second *Patala*.
- 2) In relation to this *Meda* is compared with vitreous humor in the eye ball which is a jelly like structure.
- 3) So the structure supported by vitreous humor is retina which is considered as retina.
- 4) Clinical features of third *Patala* according to *Sushruta*¹³
 - a) Patient sees only the upper part of an object but not lower part in case of involvement of third *Patala*, this type of symptoms found in case of retinal involvement.
 - b) Along with the patient patients visualized the big objects as if covered with cloths and see distorted faces as if devoid of parts like ear, nose, eyes, etc, These symptoms are correlated with marked loss of vision, which is prominent symptom in case of retinal malfunction.
- 5) In *Dristigataroga* chapter, it is mentioned that there is involvement of third *Patala* in *Pittavidaghdadristi* (day blindness), and in *kaphavidaghdadristi*¹⁴ (night blindness).
- 6) Involvement of rods and cones could be the cause for day or night blindness which are present in retinal layers.
- 7) It is nearly correlated (third *Patala*) with vitreous humor and retina.

4 *Asthyaashrita Patala*¹⁵

- 1) Fourth *Patala* is the innermost and inner to the third *Patala*.
- 2) It is constituted by *Asthi*, the hard tissue, which is supportive in function.
- 3) Nucleus of lens is considered as *Asthi* which is described as *Drishti* in *Drishtigata roga*.
- 4) In *Sushruta Sharirasthana* it is mentioned that *Tarunasthi*¹⁶ is present in *Akshikoshha* (eyeball). So this is taken as nucleus of lens which is hard and whitish structure resembling to cartilaginous bone.
- 5) Obstruction of vision occurs in respective parts where opacities are present due to affliction of fourth *Patala* by *Dosha*.
- 6) The same sign and symptoms are found in case of cortical cataract¹⁷.

- 7) Seeing of double, triple, multiple vision found in cortical cataract, also mentioned in fourth *Patala* involvement.
- 8) According to above information it is nearly correlated to fourth *Patala* with cortex of lens.

Discussion

Causes of controversy¹⁸

In *Ashtanga Hridaya Acharya Vagbhata*, mentioned prognosis of *Kshatasukra* as *Kricchasadhya* when *Twak* is affected by trauma, as *Yapya* when there is involvement of second *Patala* and as *Asadhya* when it involves the third *Patala*. Separate *Patala* is mentioned under single *Patala* (cornea) by *Vagbhata*, which is creating difference in opinion among the scholars. *Dalhana* has reversed the position of all *Patala* during the description of disease *Timira*, which is not acceptable.

According to some other views, the *Patala* is taken as different layer of retina. There is third *Patala* involvement for the disease *Pittavidaghda dristi* and *Kaphavidaghda dristi*. These are the diseases where patient complain day blindness and night blindness respectively. As the disease occurs due to degeneration of rods and cones. The *Patala* is taken as different layer of retina. But, by taking retina as *Patala*, we cannot explain the clinical entity of *Timira*.

Conclusion

1. The concise description is elaborated with the help of modern anatomy, but the difference in opinion causes difficulty in taking hold of the topic.
2. The main Manuscript like *Sushruta Samhita* requires more attention.
3. *Patala* mentioned by *Sushruta* is definitely compared with different layers of eye ball.
4. the first *Patala* is taken as Cornea, second as Uveal tract (iris, ciliary body, choroid), third as vitreous humor and retina and fourth as cortex along with capsule of lens.

Reference:

- 1) Kaviraja Shastri Ambika data,Sushruta Samhita-Part2, ,Uttartantra adhyaya1/14,Edition7th,Published by Chaukhamba Sanskrita sansthana, Varanasi 2005, P-8
- 2) Netraroga Vidnyana, A text book of Ayurvedic ophthalmology, Shalaky 1, prof.Dr. Narayana J. Vidhwansa,English translation, Vimal Vision publication, page no 221. Su.Uttarsthana 1-14
- 3) Kaviraja Shastri Ambika data,Sushruta Samhita-Part2, ,Uttartantra adhyaya1/17,Edition7th,Published by Chaukhamba Sanskrita sansthana, Varanasi 2005, P-11.
- 4) Kaviraja Shastri Ambika data,Sushruta Samhita-Part2, ,Uttartantra adhyaya1/18,Edition7th,Published by Chaukhamba Sanskrita sansthana, Varanasi 2005, P-11.
- 5) Prof. Dr. Vidhwansa N.J., Netrarogavidnyana,A textbook of Ayurvedic Ophthalmology,English translation,Shalakyatantra part-1,Published by Vimal vision,P-224
- 6) Prof. Dr. Vidhwansa N.J., Netrarogavidnyana,A textbook of Ayurvedic Ophthalmology,English translation,Shalakyatantra part-1,Published by Vimal vision,P-224
- 7) Khurana A. K., Comprehensive Ophthalmology, 6thEdition, chapter no 4, page no. 39-42.
- 8) Kaviraja Shastri Ambika data,Sushruta Samhita-Part2, ,Uttartantra adhyaya1/18,Edition7th,Published by Chaukhamba Sanskrita sansthana, Varanasi 2005, P-11.
- 9) Prof. Dr. Vidhwansa N.J., Netrarogavidnyana,A textbook of Ayurvedic Ophthalmology,English translation,Shalakyatantra part-1,Published by Vimal vision,P-222
- 10) Khurana A.K., Comprehensive Ophthalmology, 6thEdition, chapter no 4, page no. 45-49
- 11) Khurana A.K., Comprehensive Ophthalmology, 6thEdition, chapter no 8, page no. 146
- 12) Kaviraja Shastri Ambika data,Sushruta Samhita-Part2, ,Uttartantra adhyaya7/11-14,Edition7th,Published by Chaukhamba Sanskrita sansthana, Varanasi 2005, P-42.
- 13) Prof. Dr. Vidhwansa N.J., Netrarogavidnyana,A textbook of Ayurvedic Ophthalmology,English translation,Shalakyatantra part-1,Published by Vimal vision,P-225
- 14) Prof. Dr. Vidhwansa N.J., Netrarogavidnyana,A textbook of Ayurvedic Ophthalmology,English translation,Shalakyatantra part-1,Published by Vimal vision,P-223
- 15) Kaviraja Shastri Ambika data,Sushruta Samhita-Part2, ,Uttartantra adhyaya7/15,Edition7th,Published by Chaukhamba Sanskrita sansthana, Varanasi 2005, P-42.
- 16) Sushruta Samhita, Ayurved tatwa sandipika, Kaviraj Ambika data Shastri, Chaukhamba Sanskrita Sansthana, part-1, Sharirsthana, Chapter -5/24, 45
- 17) Khurana A.K., Comprehensive Ophthalmology, 6thEdition, chapter no 9, page no. 181.
- 18) Anupama patra., Journal of Science, vol 5, issue 4, 2015,238-241.

